

Exploitation and Complicity in Ken Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and Tanure Ojaide's *Great Boys: An African Childhood*

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Abstract

This paper examines exploitation and complicity in Ken Saro Wiwa's *A Month and a Day: A Detention Diary* (1995); and Tanure Ojaide's *Great Boys: An African Childhood* (1998). Through the application of Marxist criticism, it analyses how the authors reveal the excruciating pain the people of the Niger Delta had to undergo following the discovery of oil in their land since 1956 and explicate the dimensions of exploitation and complicity of the Nigerian government and the Multi-national oil companies as perpetrated against the people of the region. It also interrogates the revolutionary responses of Saro-Wiwa and Ojaide in their attempt to question and upturn strongly entrenched hegemonies in the Nigerian political economy that exploits and undermines the people of the Niger Delta. Our findings reveal the daunting effects of oil exploration activities, the massive devastation of the Niger Delta environment and of the wellbeing of the people. Consequently, the paper stylistically accounts for the use of language in depicting issues of exploitation and government complicity in Ken Saro-Wiwa, *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and Tanure Ojaide *Great Boys: An African Childhood*.

Key Words: Exploitation, Environment, Protest, Pollution, Stylistics

Resumé

Cet article examine l'exploitation et la complicité dans *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* de Ken Saro Wiwa (1995); et *Great Boys: An African Childhood* de Tanure Ojaide (1998). L'article s'appuie sur la critique marxiste pour analyser comment les auteurs révèlent la douleur atroce que les gens du Niger Delta ont dû subir suite à la découverte de pétrole dans leurs terres depuis 1956 et expliquent les dimensions d'exploitation et de complicité du gouvernement nigérian et des compagnies pétrolières internationales forgées contre les habitants de la région. Cette étude s'intéresse également aux réponses révolutionnaires de Saro-Wiwa et d'Ojaide dans leur tentative d'interroger et de renverser des hégémonies fortement enracinées dans l'économie politique nigériane qui exploite et sape les habitants du Niger Delta. Nos résultats révèlent les effets déplorable des activités d'exploration pétrolière, la dévastation massive de l'environnement du Niger Delta et du bien-être de la population. Par conséquent, cet article rend compte de l'emploi stylistique pour décrire les problèmes d'exploitation et de complicité gouvernementale dans les œuvres de Ken Saro-Wiwa et de Tanure Ojaide.

Mots-clés : Exploitation, Environnement, Contestation, Pollution, Stylistique

Introduction

The discovery of oil in commercial quantity in Oloibiri on 15 January 1956 in the

Niger Delta of Nigeria; placed Nigeria among the rank of oil-producing countries in 1958. This vibrant economic discovery in the Niger Delta became a momentous means of revenue generation for the Nigerian Government. The activities of the multi-nationals and the exploitative trends of economic consideration and environmental degradation have generated crisis, tensions and varied flow of responses as a result of exploitation and government complicity and these themes presently dominate the literature of the region. G.G. Darah foregrounds this situation thus: "...the nations and peoples of the Niger Delta have been engaged in another war, a war of verbal weapons to emancipate their territory and natural resources from the avaricious grip of the federal government and its international allies"(3).

To the Niger Deltan, this verbal war is also carried through and experienced in the literary world as major writers interrogate and explicate its excruciating pains in their minds. In his attempt to portray the temperament of Niger Delta writers, Chinyere Nwahunanya observers that:

"From those we refer to as the pioneers or patriarchs of Niger Delta Literature, we notice ab initio a dominant concern for the plight of men and the environment in the region. The literary responses were indeed aimed at highlighting the socio-economic, political, environment and other problems that have affected the human population and the flora and fauna in the region" (xiv).

Implicit in the foregoing, creative autobiography becomes a fulcrum in highlighting the effect of institutional neglect. To the Niger Deltan, land is a major factor in the development and moulding of his being. The existence and survival of the Deltan are intimately woven around the turbulent realities of oil spillage and destruction of the environment. The Niger Delta sensibility has been sharpened by socio-economic exploitation and official complicity in their responses in literature and the pattern of the people's lifestyle has been restructured due to the changes of the social conditions of the land. There is the tone of severity and submission occasioned by circumstances in the land that the people have no option then to reflect it in their literature. Niger Delta is not developed despite billions and trillions of petroleum Dollars. A place is said be developed when it attains the height of political, educational and economic advancement. Accordingly, Walter Rodney posit that:

A society develops economically as its members increase jointly their capacity for dealing with the environment. This capacity... is dependent on the extent to which they understand the laws of nature (science), on the extent to which they put that understanding into practice by devising tools (technology), and on the manner in which work is organized (10).

The region cannot deal with environmental issues because it is capital intensive. It cannot help the situation because the multi-national corporations and the Nigerian Government have "vowed" to continue oil exploration with total disregard for environmental safety measures. The multi-nationals and the Nigeria Government have made it difficult for the people to attain freedom as a result of domestic colonialism and the virtual destruction of the environment. It is therefore pertinent that the literature of Niger Delta protests and captures these crises and the dilemma of oil-producing region as the government and multi-

nationals have refused to clean up the pollution resulting from explorations. The writers are victims of the collective brutalization of the people of the region, *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and *Great Boys: An African Childhood* give insight to the problem of the people and stir them to conscious action.

Marxism aids the realisation of meaning within this discourse, Marxism originated from the *Communist Manifesto* by Marx, Engels and Lenin. Communist doctrine is predicated on an ideal society in which everything is equally shared. Marxism is a movement that is founded upon the ideology of the emancipation of the working class, subduing all forms of domination by the bourgeoisie. While Marxism stands for the destruction of the capitalist state and has as its aim in the withering away from the state all forms of institutionalized violence, the Marxist does not only support the rights of the working class to exercise a domination over the bourgeoisie, they actively fight for that. The society, from which an artist originates, in most cases, informs the issues he writes about. It is a valid truth that literature is not created in a vacuum as it mediates on social-political issues that the artist grapples with in his existence. Charles Bressler gives vent to the above when he says that:

...society shapes our consciousness; that social and economic conditions directly influences how what we believe and values and that Marxism offers us an opportunity and a plan for changing the world from a play of bigotry, hatred and conflict resulting from class struggle to classless society, where wealth, opportunity and education are actually accessible for all people (115).

Tanure Ojaide and Ken Saro-Wiwa find themselves in a society that is characterized by a distinctive social stratification, featuring the oppressed and the oppressor. Both Ken Saro-Wiwa and Tanure Ojaide call for a non-violent revolution that will overthrow the bourgeoisie class that is represented by the Nigerian Government and the multinationals. They, therefore, adopt the Marxist ideology. Nwahunanya admits that;

“Creative works of literature are the products of the society’s libido. The psychological approach may illuminate the creative process, but the goings-on in the psyche itself are not central as such to literature since they are only preparatory to the act of creation and psychological truths become artistic values only if they enhance coherence and complexity in a work (36).

The reason for the foregoing is that the writer is an active participant in his society and by extension recreates the collective experiences of the people. The African experience thus transcends the concept of “Art for Art’s sake” theory but performs a function in the society in which it thrives and emerges into a moralistic light in the questioning of societal practices.

Autobiography as a Literary Form

The autobiography is a literary form and shares aesthetic elements with other literary genres. Alfred Kazin is of the same conviction when he says, “Autobiography like other literary forms, is what a gifted writer makes out of it” (211). Implicit in the foregoing is that autobiography requires artistic ingenuity at its realisation of a piece. The “I” element, which is the first person narrative technique, becomes the signing mark of an autobiography. Rosy

Singh identifies one of the dominant characters of autobiography thus; “The most intriguing signifier of autobiographical is the first person “I” whereby the author, the narrator, as well as the protagonist, are one and the same” (80).

Consequently, the first person narrative technique becomes a literary definition in an attempt to classify autobiography. Singh further observes other qualities of an autobiography, “...the genre autobiography has mostly focused on individual experience often marked by a literary language and a sophisticated mode of presentation of a specific group, often socially disadvantaged...” (85). Autobiography is individual experiences that chronicle the plight of the collective, using the individual as a representation of the whole through the use of literary language.

The autobiography like other literary works is a quest narrative that interrogates the subjection of a group of people. Singh accounted for this in autobiography as a means of political vent to challenge the status quo- “with the protagonist in the role of a victim or a witness or both” (85). The autobiography is first a historical experience of an individual as a victim or witness or both which the writer appropriate to make a case for the plight of his people. George Gusdof comments on the literary form of autobiography that: “The past that is recalled has lost its flesh and bone solidity, but has won a new and more intimate relationship to the individual life that can thus, after being long dispersed and sought again though. In the course of time, be rediscovered and drawn together again beyond time” (85).

The autobiography is a quasi-fictional representation of events so significant that it is worth remembering as a historical marker of the subjection or continuous subjugation of a people in a political system. Jennifer Jensen Wallach says “autobiography is a peculiar genre, which purports to be both literature and history but not entirely one or the other” (446). Autobiography is a hybrid narrative of history and literature of oppressed individual and the collectives. However, sometimes it captures individual’s achievements with the collective milestone of a generation.

According to Leonard Onwugbuche, “...an autobiography is an account of one’s own life. It is a form of biography in which the subject is the author...autobiography is seen as a deliberate literary product” (16). From the foregoing, it is obvious that autobiography contains the life and times of the writer which we might consider important and highly influential to the emergence of his achievements. This is so, in the sense that it is “a deliberate literary product” (16) and the said output of the “product” must have a utility value to the consuming literary readers. Onwugbuche further asserts that “...it is important to recognize that the deliberate or conscious effort is fuelled by certain motives. This may be confessional in which the driving force behind it is the need to unburden one’s self of a feeling of guilt” (16). However, expounding core of the foregoing, not all unburdening is tilted toward the purgation of a guilty heart but “certain motives” in the society which tend to hold the writer and his society captive in psychological, economic and political dimensions of life which are the Meta elements of freedom. Leslie Stephen offers a very clear explanation, “The true autobiography is written by one who feels an irresistible longing for confidential expression; one who is forced by his innate constitution to unburden himself to the public of the kind of matter generally for our close intimacy” (259). From the above explication, autobiography, like most literary pieces in the world, is a speaking art that sheds light on issues that are personal to the autobiographer and contains a

liberating light to the society and posterity that come in contact to it. Autobiography is a form of interrogative literary piece; it is in most cases a response to the society in which it strives, as the writer tries to justify and indict certain elements and actions of the masses and the leaders thereby leading to the purgation of the mind of the artist and igniting the desire for change.

One of the dominant features of autobiography is not necessarily the total capturing of the day to day experiences of the author, but the capturing of the exceptional experiences of the author and the portrayal of the said experiences to the enlightenment and liberation of man in his struggle in life as can be seen in the autobiographies of Chukuma C. Ibezute (*Rediscovering My Mission*), Mahatma Gandhi (*The Story of My Experiment with the Truth*) and Ken SaroWiwa (*A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary*). SaroWiwa makes a case for the functionality of literature including autobiography when he submits that:

...it being my credo that literature in a critical situation such as Nigeria's cannot be devoid of politics. Indeed, literature must serve society by steeping itself in politics, by intervention, and writers must not write merely to amuse or to take a bemused, critical look at the society. They must play an interventionist role. My experience has been that African governments can ignore writers, taking comfort in the fact that only few read and write, and that those who read find little time for the luxury of literary consumption beyond the need to pass examination based on set texts. Therefore, the writer must be *L'homme engage*: the intellectual man of action. He must take part in mass organization.(81).

It is this conviction that motivated Saro-Wiwa to be confrontational and take literature into the streets to inform the Nigerian society about the unjustified exploitation of his people, since the vast populace of the "Nigerian society does not read". It is this interventionist role that is the core of Saro-Wiwa's engagement of the force of exploitation in his autobiography. *A Month and a Day* is an account of a grown up man speaking with grown-ups in his attempt to liberate his people from withering condition. Saro-Wiwa has played this intervention role in almost all of his literary works that the Nigerian government felt uncomfortable and had to eliminate him from the surface of the earth. However, his postulations in literary lines are still playing the role he was passionate about.

Tanure Ojaide in *Great Boys: An African Childhood* delves into the issue of exploitation and official complicity but in a subtle manner. He tells the story of his glorious childhood and invariably indicts the Nigerian Government and the multi-nationals as a bilateral party to the dehumanization and degradation prevalent in the Niger Delta region. Thus, Ojaide advocates the use of non-violent protest through literary lines no matter how long it last. This is seen in his authorial presentation of the problems of Niger which was more of a passive illustration of the plights of the people of the Niger Delta, unlike Saro-Wiwa who is an active advocate and confrontational against exploitation.

Exploitation in Tanure Ojaide's *The Great Boys: An African Childhood*

The discovery of oil and its exploration in Niger Delta has led to various levels of

environmental pollution such as destruction of aquatic lives, deforestation, noise pollution and aridity of land among others. The above are explicated and examined. According to Marx, "history and therefore our understanding of people and their actions and belief is determined by economic conditions" (166). *The Great Boys: An African Childhood* is a revolutionary piece directed to the youths and adults from other regions. The autobiography explores with subtle portrayal, the consequences of the activities of oil exploration of multi-nationals in the Niger Delta region. It portrays the various effects of oil exploration activities in the region as examined under the literary interrogation. Ojaide through the telling of his childhood experiences retells the story of his people and subtly incites them to rebel against oppression. The interrogation of the text reveals that the coming of Shell in October 1958 was more or less the dawn of deforestation:

Sometime after the rains in 1958, about late October, Shell-BP came.

A lot of people, from cities, came to our area. They came wearing helmets, in pickups jeep....they tore through forests, through rubber plantations, through farmlands and through creeks, cutting paths....The opposite direction cleared into the bush to make way for the other (126).

The deforestation of the Niger Delta environment represented at the start of oil exploration activities in 1958 was more than a military invasion that affected all aspects of the people's existence. The "tore through" (126) according to Ojaide was a comprehensive one in the sense that the forest, farmland, rubber plantations among other economic and environmental trees were affected by capitalist oil exploration and exploitation. Not only was their environment destroyed, their means of livelihood is destroyed as a result of this significant "tore through". However, the forest lost its peace to a new dawn of economic civilization and the actions of the Nigerian government and multi-nationals in the Niger Delta region. Ojaide accentuates the above when he states that:

The forest was no longer a quiet place, sounds of heavy trucks carrying huge machines, some tall in conical fashion, broke the quiet of the area. The boisterous noise of workers, elated by their oyibo work that earned them a fortune shattered the legendary silence of the rustic landscape (126).

This is more than a poet's lamentation in *The Deserted Village* but this is an Ojaide's lament in *The Great Boys: An African Childhood* of what has seized the peace of the Niger Delta and its environs and an attempt to question political authority thereby up-turning the capitalist trend. The multi-nationals did not stop at deforestation and the invasion of peace but new dimensions were introduced to proceed with their on-slaughter. Ojaide portrays this new dimension thus:

We used to lie outside in the early part of the night to tell stories. We fell asleep most times and woke when it was cool enough to sleep in the house. Then one day, we awoke to an intense heat and a monstrous cloud of fire in the sky. Nobody knew what type of fire rose so high as to threaten God.... I woke from sleep in a panic and in a dazed frenzy of the strange brightness in a supposedly dark night shouted for help(126).

The eternal day which is meant for those with heavenly hope is set forever in the existence of the Niger Delta region as a result of the refining fire of crude oil. The people of the region

are exposed to hazardous gases. The carbon emission by the exploration companies threatens their existence. Ojaide continues:

That fire of God or of a demon became the symbol of the national economy. Nobody saw where the oil was being produced, with the exception of where there had been a broken pipe. The oil was piped to Ughelli or to Port Harcourt and into ships that sail overseas. The villages and towns around the oil wells have been “compensated” by the oil company, and they had to endure the heat and the angry gods of fire that lit their night into eternal dawn(126).

This shows the effects of oil exploration in the Niger Delta region. It is a micro representation of the macro plights of resource curse and oppressed people of the Niger Delta. The foregoing captures the resultant damage on the totality of the people’s life. Ojaide laments:

Within months a pipeline broke and the streams were covered with thick seams. The fish floated belly-up, and no one would eat dead fish. Hunters discovered that bush animals were becoming rare sight. The grasscutters and antelopes appeared to have relocated to quieter and darker places. Farmers saw their cassava and yam leaves wilt and burnout. Of course, the underground tubers were shrivelled and couldn’t be eaten. (126 – 127)

Oil exploration activities can be considered as a new art of creation which is opposed to already created divine environment. Oil spillage does not only destroy agricultural and aquatic lives visible to Ojaide but it also destroys other marine lives. The destruction of the wildlife as a result of oil spillage leads to the destruction of the people in the sense that their means of sustenance is completely destroyed and their environment is completely contaminated. Ojaide appropriates the history of oppression in the Niger Delta to incite rebellion. The text highlights the indifference of government as a call to motivate the people to protect themselves from exploitation. He further argues that: “The oil companies were part of government, and who could tell it to leave? As my Grandma put it, “If the moon does not shine well, who will go to the sky to put it right?” Government is a sacred animal like the iguana of the Orogun people, and whoever hurts or kills it will incur damnation” (127). The people of the Niger Delta have been incurring such damnation not because the people touched the government but because the oil exploitation is a deadly necessity to drive a traditional economy that is oil focused. The cutting down of trees and oil spillage affect the soil texture and it invariably leads to aridity. The above arises from the short-sightedness of multi-nationals and the Nigerian government to understand that the trees in the environment perform a profound function in the environment and in the lives of individuals and agricultural produce. This is evident in Ojaide’s speech:

We are not land people; we are not an open country people. As I grew, I saw the trees axed away, despite the forest... I saw trees cut down to drive away the fear of witches. In a frenzy, trees were felled. No trees... Everywhere was becoming bare, and water was driven away for more land.

For the first time I began to hear that there was little left of farmland, that the only land worth farming was the distant piece in Uyo, where there was no new oil and no village around. (127)

The action of the multi-nationals in the Niger Delta has actually led to sterility in the once fertile land of the Niger Delta. The indiscriminate cutting down of trees to drive away the “witches” the people were used to is enough to batter the people’s psyche and destroy their environment. In the name of driving away witches, the multi-nationals and the Nigerian government exposed the earth surface to direct rays from the sun and it invariably affected micro and macro organisms in the soil. We can strongly aver that the actions of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals have actually contributed greatly to climate change in Nigeria and the harsh realities of environmental responses of excess rainfall and flooding in most parts of the Niger Delta. Ojaide adduces to the above when he asserts that:

At night the gas flame lit the sky and almost consumed the moon that I had grown up with. The harmattan months lost their cool to the flaring gas, which had brought eternal heat. Once in a while dead ants littered empty spaces. They might have been sacrificed to the fire god that held the wealth of the black gold. (130)

The new creations of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals have an adverse effect on the Niger Delta region. It is the height of environmental pollution that has led to the death of several organisms that act as organ decomposers to planted crops before they germinate. Finally, Ojaide in capturing the material relationship and its exploitation in the Niger Delta hopes that by so doing they would be a reversal of the plight of the masses in the region.

Official Complicity in Ken Saro-Wiwa’s *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary*

Through Ken Saro-Wiwa’s non-violent protests and his interactions with the agents of the Nigerian government, we see various shades of human rights violation. Saro-Wiwa was arrested and illegally imprisoned because of his outspokenness and non-violent protest against the violation of his people’s collective right to existence as is of the divine entrustment to all beings. This is evident in Ken Saro-Wiwa’s speech: “...before me was an armed security man flagging the car down, his rifle pointing at my chauffeur’s head. Then, just as suddenly, more security men in mufti headed for the rear of the door of the car, swung it open, and ordered me to get down”(3). The Nigerian Government was willing to send the whole barrack after a defenceless civilian with absolute disregard for his sanity. Ken Saro-Wiwa’s arrest on 21 June 1993 at UTC junction in Port Harcourt was more like a military invasion than an arrest. The sight of the security personnel was enough to drive Ken Saro-Wiwa into insanity. Saro-Wiwa avers, “...I was asked to write a statement about my activities on Election Day, 12 June 1992. The Ogoni, under the leadership of the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP), had boycotted the election. I asked perfunctorily to be allowed to see my lawyer before committing myself to paper. The request was turned down” (5). Saro-Wiwa’s desire to galvanize his people to form a common front like other ethnic groups in the country was considered as an aberration in a

state that prides itself as a secular state. He was arrested, interrogated and stripped off his innocence, even when the Nigerian law states that an accused is presumed innocent until proven guilty beyond reasonable doubt by law court. His people's free will whether to vote or not to vote was called into question. He was molested because of Ogoni moral right take a decision. Saro-Wiwa continues: "...the senior police officer told me that on Election Day, 12 June 1992, Policemen had been made to frog jump people in Ogoni and there had been disturbance"(6). There has been constant physical and psychological molestation of Saro-Wiwa in the sense that he became a regular inmate of the police station. In *A Month and a Day: a Detention Diary* there is a symbiotic relationship between human right violation and constant resistance by those whose rights are violated. This is highlighted in the case of the youths of Ogoni who had to react against their leaders being arrested for their outspokenness against their subjugation. Ken Saro-Wiwa asserts thus:

I was to learn later that Ogoni youths had shown far more solidarity, far more courage than I had credited them with. Not knowing what had happened to me. They had gone in a group of 500 or more to the offices of SSS and opened every single door in an effort to take me. And when they had found me there, they had gone to the central Police station in Port Harcourt, where they engaged the riot police in a struggle. They picked up canisters of tear gas shot by the police before they could explode and threw them back to their tormentors. They tore down a part of the brick wall which fenced off the police station from the rest of the town. And almost all night they lit bonfires along Aggrey Road to place a distance between the brutality ...themselves. They made sure that the town of Port Harcourt heard their protest at my arrest. And no one could stop them. (18).

And one sees from the above not the celebration of violence, but the resilience of an oppressed people. It shows that human nature cannot endure the constant battering from so-called superior authorities. We can aver that the above is a defining characteristic of most oppressed people in the world in general and the Ogoni people in particular. Poor infrastructure, the use of brutality and suppression of their voices and total neglect of the environment are some of the plights of the region that generates the wealth of the Nigerian nation. It is ironical that the depleting resources of the Niger Delta are not used for their own development as a people; they are used neither for the development of human capital nor for the development of infrastructure in the environs rather they are now a curse to their existence. Ken Saro-Wiwa affirms in lamentation: "The state road irked me. It was one of my over riding concerns. Not the road itself, but the fact that in this rich, oil bearing area, the roads should be so rickety, while in the North of Nigeria, in that arid part of the country, there were wide express ways constructed at great cost with the petrodollars which the Delta belched forth. The injustice of it cried to the heavens" (19).

Irrespective of how we tend to examine the above issue, it is an open secret that petrodollars were used to build better roads in the North, East and West while those whose land generates the resources have no road . Niger Delta is not a place to be or to boast of

although it provides the nation's wealth; this is as a result of the nature of its environment, no thanks to oil exploration activities. He further asserts that:

The population of Lagos had exploded once oil money from the Delta had been cornered by the nations rulers and transferred to Lagos from hapless communities like the Ogoni and the Ijaws who were too few to defend their inheritance....most of that money was also spent on foreign luxuries like cars, and soon the few roads in the city were clogged with cars, rendering movement well nigh impossible. Overhead bridges became the norms of this city" (33-34).

This dramatizes the neglect of the region. It is this neglect that led to Ogoni Bill of Rights on 26 August 1990, which was tilted toward the liberation of the people from exploitation and enshrining of resource control. The most painful part of it is that Nigeria made billions from the resources in the Niger Delta and still ran into debt and none of this debt was tailored to human capital or infrastructural development in the Niger Delta.

However, Ken Saro-Wiwa highlights the brutal realities of neglect and abject poverty in the description of the recklessness of the Nigerian government and states thus: "Nigeria has an external debt of over thirty billion dollars. None of that debt was incurred on any project in the Ogoni area or any project remotely beneficial to the Ogonis. The International Monetary Fund and The World Bank, capitalizing on the payment of the debt, are encouraging intensified exploitation of oil and gas, which constitute 94 percent of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product" (97). The poverty level of the people of the Niger Delta is at a high level and compounded by lack of infrastructure.

The effect of oil exploration in the region is alarming, the people cannot grow crops in a polluted land neither can they fish from it. Saro-Wiwa's words describe the above when he asserts that:

The Ogoni people have settled in this area as farmers and fishermen since remembered and had established a well organized social system ...petroleum was discovered in Ogoni in 1958 and since then an estimated US hundred billion dollars' worth of oil and gas has been carted away from Ogoni land. In return for this, the Ogoni people have received nothing. Oil exploration has turned Ogoni into a wasteland: lands, streams, and creeks are totally and continuously polluted; the atmosphere has been poisoned, charged as it is with hydrocarbon vapours...Acid rain, oil spillage and oil blowouts have devastated Ogoni territory. High-pressure oil pipelines crisscross the surface of Ogoni farmlands and villages dangerously (95-96).

The above captures a society that does not guarantee the existence of its citizenry but punishes them to death. The Nigerian system has succeeded in favouring few while punishing and neglecting the teeming population of the region. We can aver that oil exploration and its spillage is one of the drivers of unemployment in the Niger Delta. It is true that oil exploration in the Niger Delta has resulted in hardship, inequality and a psychological trauma for the people whose land breed employment for others and billions of

dollars while it breeds penury and unemployment for the people of Niger Delta. This is captured in Ken Saro-Wiwa's speech:

The result of such unchecked environmental pollution and degradation include the complete destruction of the eco system. Mangrove forests have fallen to the toxicity of oil and are being replaced by noxious nypapalms; the rain forest has fallen to the axe of the multinational oil companies, all wildlife is dead, marine life is gone, the farmlands have been rendered infertile by acid rain and the once beautiful Ogoni countryside is no longer a source of fresh air and green vegetation. All one sees and feels around is death. Environmental degradation has been a lethal weapon in the war against the indigenous Ogoni people. Incidental to and indeed compounding this ecological devastation is the political marginalization and complete oppression of the Ogoni and especially the denial of their rights, including land rights. (96).

A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary is an analysis of a failing Nigerian system, its economic construct and politics. The autobiography captures the socio economic deprivation of the citizens as a result of their means of livelihood being destroyed by oil exploration. Ken Saro-Wiwa adopts an interrogative lament approach in the autobiography. He and his people are caught in the ravaging union called Nigeria and in the tragedy of survival. *A Month and a Day: A Detention Diary* encapsulates the lamentations and frustration of the people of the Niger Delta over a dislodging power of resource curse that threatens their existence and strips them of their sanity and means of livelihood. Ogoni land as well as Niger Delta is in a near Hiroshima and Nagasaki state. Except something is done, the assaults and casualties caused by unemployment and smothering of their existence will be greater than that which befell two cities hit by the atomic bomb of August 6, 1945. This portrayal of the after effect of socio-economic stratification of contemporary society calls attention to the issues so far raised to enable the people benefit from their resources by not a divine act but by those who are greater than them. Multi-nationals and the Nigerian government use their military might to dispose the people of their land and resources. *A Month and a Day: A Detention Diary* is a harvest of tears against such smothering dispossession as perpetuated by the Economic twines of the Niger Delta (Nigerian government and multi-nationals). The autobiographer cries out:

On 30 April, disaster struck. Shell had been dualizing the Tran-Niger Pipeline, which carries oil from most parts of the delta through Ogoni territory to the export terminal at Bonny. They had not carried out an environmental impact assessment study. They had not negotiated with the landlords whose land they were using and/ or desecrating. They simply got soldiers of the Nigerian army to guard them,...the soldiers had gone through a number of Ogoni villages, but when they got to Biara, where a major oil spill had polluted the streams and the land two years earlier, incensed villagers, mostly women, turned out to question them. The women held twigs as they had been advised to do to indicate that they were protecting peacefully. The soldiers emptied their live ammunition on them

(156).

The above scenario captures the fate of the Niger Delta. Not only are they dispossessed, but they are also killed in the process if they dare to question their exploiters and die in the process if they keep quiet. The multi-nationals operating in the Niger Delta region carry out their oil exploration without applying environmental safety measures. The peoples' lands are seized by force and they are left without a means of livelihood. Forceful military intervention and environmental degradation occasioned by oil spillage has dispossessed the people, physically, economically and psychologically. Ken Saro-Wiwa asserts:

I have to state that MOSOP did not stop Shell, although though we did let it be known that the company was persona non grata in our land because of its destruction of the environment, its uncaring exploitation of the community, and its refusal to make any restitution whatsoever for the harm it had done to the Ogoni people and environment.(160)

The cries of yesterday are still heard in Ogoni land in particular and in the Niger Delta in general. The attitude of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals has been business as usual in their resolve to prevent the people from benefiting from their resources. Saro-Wiwa argues further: "I consider the loss of the Niger River Delta a loss to all mankind and therefore regard Shell's despoliation of the area as a crime to all humanity" (168). The agents of government and multi-nationals did not only succeed in depriving the people of the benefits of their depleting resources but they go as far as destroying the Niger Delta Rivers which are a means of livelihood and survival. *A Month and a Day: A Detention Diary* and *Great Boys: An African Childhood* are protest autobiographies against exploitation and official complicity; these are the major motifs that crisscross the two autobiographies. The two autobiographies give multi-dimensional views of the problems of the Niger Delta. Saro-Wiwa and Ojaide in their works portray exploitation and official complicity as a synthesis of the problem of the Niger Delta. This synthesis, which is a catalyst for frustration, social inequality and dehumanization of the people of the region, becomes combustion for the revolutionary violence in both works. Violence is employed as an interrogative liberating force of the people of the Niger Delta and as a means of class-consciousness which tends to highlight the glorious past of the region, its gory present and its bleak future as a result of oil exploration activities. Ken SaroWiwa in *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and TanureOjaide's *The Great Boys: An African Childhood* are autobiographies that depict the symbiotic relationship between government complicity and exploitation. There is the idea of exploitation-induced deforestation and environmental degradation by the actions of the Nigerian government and multi-nationals. The autobiographies capture a society that is in a constant state of captivity as a result of the resources or better still 'curses' in their soil.

The works capture the irony of existence as the resources from the region are a blessing to just a few but a curse to the owners of the land, the masses. It shows how the inhumanity of the new creation of the Nigerian government and its ally, the multi-nationals dehumanize

and batter the existence of the people of the Niger Delta. *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* deals with Saro-Wiwa's direct confrontation with the exploitative economic alliance of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals. It is Saro-Wiwa's conscious motivation of the people of the Niger Delta to rebel against the conspiracy of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals in their region. There is the Marxist revival in the consciousness of the Niger Deltans. Ken Saro-Wiwa actively participates in the struggle to liberate his people from economic captivity. He travelled both far and near to plead the cause of his people and, on each occasion, he emphasized through his speeches that the only offence his people have committed against Nigeria is the possession of oil in their land. The resources in the Niger Delta kill the people in an "unconventional way" as we have already explicated in the body of this discourse. Ken Saro-Wiwa's lamented against the Nigerian government and multi-nationals to the international community and called them to come to the aid of his people, and each trip he made strengthened his conviction of the guiltlessness of his people. Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* calls the attention of the international community to compel the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals to bear full responsibility of their new creation in the belaboured land of Niger Delta. *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* is Saro-Wiwa's litigation against the exploitive construct of the Nigerian system.

Stylistics Dimensions in *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and *The Great Boys: An African Childhood*

Stylistics explores how language is used in a literary text to arrive at meaning. It accounts for how a writer makes use of words in the construction of the world of the narrative. Paul Simpson defines stylistics as "...a method of textual interpretation in which primacy of place is assigned to language" (3).

Motif

Motif is a literary thematic restatement that is connected symbolically to the chain of the narrative. Land is the autographical motif in the portrayal of exploitation leading to degradation in the Niger Delta within world of the texts in particular and by extension in the Niger Delta region. The centrality of this land-motif to the Niger Delta literary piece is a form of rebellion. Essienubong H. Ikpe emphasizes the helplessness of the people when he states that, "Successive governments of Nigeria have exploited the resources of this region with reckless abandon" (1). This exploitation and reckless abandon have stirred responses of creative ingenuity from writers within and outside the region. The virtual destruction of the environment and its attendant effects on all facets of the people's way of life has created an increasing feeling of insecurity, estrangement from the land. The motif of exploitation and official complicity in the works of Ken Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and Tanure Ojaide's *The Great Boys: An African Childhood* portrays the exploitation of the land which is their "being" and has sharpened Niger Deltans sensibility to socio-economic injustice and official complicity in Nigeria to the extent that they have resisted such trend. In their responses in literature and the pattern of the peoples' life style has been restructured by the changes of socio conditions of the land. There is this tone of severity and submission occasioned by circumstances which now reflects in their literature. Nwahunanya

posits that;

As the land bleed oil, so the people tears in their abject poverty and real blood as they fall under the constant assault of government agents bent to silence their protests. The writers have through creative literature increased their pressures on sensitive minds in their call for a dispassionate reconsideration of the environmental and Human rights issues which have repeatedly constituted their thematic focus” (xvi).

Land-motif in *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* discusses the issue of environmental pollution and deforestation as a result of Oil spillage and the complacency of the Nigerian government that benefits solely from the proceeds of petroleum to arrest the situation. Ken Saro-Wiwa (1995), captures the severity of their situation thus:

Today, the Ogoni people are involved in two grim wars. The first is the 35 year old ecological war waged by the multinational oil companies, Shell and Chevron. In this most sophisticated and unconventional war, no bones are broken, no blood is spilled and no one is maimed. Yet, man, woman and children die; flora and fauna perish, the air and water are poisoned and finally, the land die. The second war is a Tyranny, oppression and greed designed to dispose the Ogoni people of their wealth and subjects them to abject poverty, slavery, dehumanization and extinction. (148).

Ken Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day: Detention Diary* interrogates and awakens the consciousness of the people from these unilateral wars against them as prosecuted by the Nigerian government and multi-nationals. Ken Saro-Wiwa's autobiography aims at the deconstructing a society that is exploitatively constructed and to stir up the psyche of the people to defend themselves thereby defending the land. A cardinal motif in Tenure Ojaide's *Great Boys: An Africa Childhood* is passion for the environment, for his early childhood which portrays his peoples' agrarian experiences that is now destroyed by multinationals. He says: "Every day's need was provided by the creeks and streams. Nobody fretted over food there was always fish or bush meat for whenever you wanted to cook or eat. Many times I roasted fish or meat to accompany roasted yam and plantain, which the oil was delicious and I kept them in my mouth for long to relish the savor" (70-71). The author's overwhelming passion for his environment, for an anchorage, streams from the chaos created by multinationals in his environs. Ojaide's concern for a connection, for accommodation, he portrays a typical Niger Delta region when the land was at "peace". To the Niger Deltan, land is a major factor in his development and moulding of his mind. The existence and survival of the Deltans are intimately woven around the turbulent reality of oil spillage and destruction of the environment. The Niger Delta sensibility has been sharpened by the socio-economic exploitation and official complicity. The autobiographies highlight the pattern of the people's lifestyle as they have been restructured due to the changes in the social conditions of the land.

Narrative Choice

Ken Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and Tanure Ojaide's *Great Boys*:

An African Childhood makes use of “I” as a narrative choice in fashioning the world of the autobiographies. The use of “I” which is a personal pronoun in the texts shows that the writers are participant within the scope of the narrative. Nina Norgaard et-al in an attempt to account for a narrator posit that the “...narrator...is typically the entity or agent that tells the story”. They note further that, “the prominent role of the telling voice that singularise narrative as a distinctive type of communicative event” (125). The first person narrative voice becomes a distinctive type of the communication nature within the world of two autobiographies. The autobiographer uses “I” to call attention to themselves as a single representation of the collective and by extension the land which is they being. The oppression of the “I” is the oppression of the land and exploitation and degradation of it. There is no distinction between the being and the land within the texts because their people suffer from the pain inflicted on the land. Rosy Singh notes that in an autobiography the narrator can embody the protagonist and victim within the text as seen in the autobiographies interrogated.

Tone

The tone of the narrative can be accounted for based on the narrator’s voice within the world of the autobiographies. Saro-Wiwa’s voice in *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* is confrontational and inciting to protest oppression and incite rebel. Saro-Wiwa sees the liberation of his people as beyond mere intellectual struggle but must have a physical undertone. Saro-Wiwa is a town crier that awakens the people to the reality of their exploitation. Consequently, he uses the language of struggle, “protest”, “solidarity”, confrontation, etc.

Saro-Wiwa describes his role as the leader of the struggle which highlights the tone of the narrative thus: “They had been sleepwalking their way towards extinction, not knowing what internal colonialism had done and was doing to them. It has fallen on me to wake them up from the sleep of the century and I had accepted the full responsibility for doing so.” (18). this tone of protest and awaking up his people in the struggle is woven round the world of the narrative and is confrontation sometimes leading to violence in the narrative. He, thus, accounts for his activist approach to literature when he states that; “Literature must serve society by steeping itself in politics, by intervention, and writers must not merely write to amuse or take a bemused, critical look at the society. They must play an interventionist role” (81). This “interventionist role”, Saro-Wiwa, the victim and the protagonist of the text understudy. He intellectually captures the levels of exploitation in the Niger Delta and presents it to the government through mass protest and civil disobedience.

The tone in *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* is harsh and somewhat insults the perpetrators of socio-political exploitation of the people and the land of Niger Delta. Tanure Ojaide’s *The Great Boys: An African Child* is also engaged in protest against the exploitation of his people, but it is done subtly by showing and allowing the people to make the decision for themselves. His tone plays a sort of psychological note on us by presenting to us the nature of the land, the existence of the land before the coming of the oil multi-national thus: “I always drew out the yam tuber or the cassava from the ground whole. The entire robust, no matter the force I put into the pulling, came out whole. I harvested corn, and the cob was big and fully seeded. When I cut the plantain the bunch remained whole

despite its crash to ground”(39). The tone is mild as he narrates the nature of the land before the advent of the multi-national companies. He goes further to juxtapose the past condition of the land with the presence of the multi-national. Yet, he lives the decision making to his people. He states sardonically, “Fishermen and women soon discovered that they couldn’t catch as many fish as they used to. Rumors had it that Mammy Water or the water goddess had withdrawn to the sea with her retinue of fish from river over which black oil light shone” (126). In a subtle and mild tone, the narrator tells the story of his being as that of the collective experience of his people. But he does not instigate them to action. He leaves that decision to them.

Similarly, Tanure uses non-violent revolution to demand for the right of his people. A non-violent revolution is a revolution using mostly campaigns of civil resistance, nonviolent-protest to bring about the departure of a government seen as tyrannical. This concept of non-violence is seen in Ken SaroWiwa’s *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* and Tanure Ojaide’s *Great Boys: An African Childhood*, these autobiographies portray disillusionment and exploitation that constitute the social realities of the majority of the Niger Delta region.

The authors succinctly display their contempt for the agents of exploitation and degradation of the environment. While Ken Saro-Wiwa’s approach is peaceful protest and non-violent direct confrontation with the forces of exploitation with a clarion call for resource control by the people. Tanure Ojaide’s approach is a subtle presentation of how the comings of multi-national have set in doom in the Niger Delta region. His motive is to awaken the people to the past “glories” of the region and its environment. While Tanure Ojaide entertains and informs, hoping that it will lead to a revolution in the society, Saro-Wiwa directly demands for a revolution within the world of the narrative and in reality. Although the historical canon of the world is replicated with instance of revolution that varied in terms of the method and motivations but the end product in most cases has always been the change in the socio-political and economic construct of the society.

Conclusion

Literature has always kept faith with the realities of the human society. This is the cognitive truth in the literature emanating from the Niger Delta, which is predominantly protest literature and cuts across all genres in the literature of the region. The dominant theme that pervades both Tanure Ojaide’s *The Great Boys: An African Childhood* and Ken Saro-Wiwa’s *A Month and A Day: A Detention Diary* is revolt against exploitation and official complicity. These two autobiographies have unmasked the anomalies in the Niger Delta. Through the creative imagination of Saro-Wiwa and Ojaide, we see the complicity of the Nigerian government and the multi-nationals in their exploitation and degradation of the environment of the Niger Delta.

The autobiographies call for a rebellion against the impediment on the people’s existence and are convincing representations of the Nigerian economic and political climate. Saro-Wiwa and Tanure Ojaide are Marxist writers who are concerned with the plight of the masses and seek to deconstruct the machines of exploitation. The work explicates how the Nigerian government has failed to take up her responsibility but rather prey on the people of the Niger Delta. The authorial vision in the texts interrogates the loss of sanity of existence

as a result of the trend of oil exploration and the prevailing wreckage it heaps on the people. Saro-Wiwa and Ojaide, write in response to bilateral economic and political decimation of the people of the Niger Delta. So far, the interrogated text highlights the social ills inherent in Nigeria and it seeks for social justice.

The autobiographies raise biting issues in the polity of the national life, such as deforestation, aridity of land, destruction of aquatic lives, poor infrastructure and unemployment, politic of disposition among others. In *A month and a Day: a Detention Diary* the comprehensive repression and oppression of the people is explored and called into question. The autobiographies offer the reader a keen insight into the illusion of realities that exists in the Niger Delta region. Ojaide's *Great Boys: An African Childhood* chronicles the deprivation and exploitation of the people as a result of the rich deposit of oil in their land. The autobiographies have established that the problem of the Niger Delta is that of the comprehensive neglect of successive Nigerian governments and the refusal of the multi-nationals to operate in the region with safety measures.

In conclusion, Ken Saro-Wiwa and Tanure Ojaide in their autobiographies laid an enduring legacy that will fight the exploitative conglomerate of the Nigerian system as it regards the issue of the Niger Delta. They use their autobiographies to reawaken the consciousness of the people of the Niger Delta and to encourage them to rebel against the forces that exploit them and threaten their existence. Both texts capture the stark realities of the Niger Delta region.

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